

Gaming for learning

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057760>

Abstract

In the subject of wave optics, we seek to involve students in their learning through active learning techniques. Students participate in large group classes doing small activities, competition games, solving problems,... They are also very active in the laboratory sessions (half the total time of the course) where they measure and analyze the contents developed at the large sessions. The activities they play in the large group are based on gamification principles; students answer group quizzes and get a ranking based on whether or not they get the right answer. We have set out to better develop the possibilities of game-based learning by redesigning the simulation activities that students carry out based on the principles of McGonigal¹ so that they are games from which they cannot escape without learning. The simulation activities have been included in an escape room where students play in groups and to advance in the game they must solve a riddle using the knowledge developed in the subject. As McGonigal proposes, the escape room seeks to have an epic mission, a clear goal, immediate feedback and another chance to prove it, and a positive social dimension.

Keywords: Active Learning; game-based learning, serious games, motivation.

1 Introduction

Gamification has entered strongly into many areas of training, training for industry⁵, training for the financial sector⁶, and of course university education (Call, 2021; Lopez-Fernandez, 2021). Game-based learning has gained significant notoriety in recent years, accompanied by the development of computer tools that facilitate the implementation of quizzes, competitions, simulations, WebQuests, escape rooms, ...

Both the gamification of educational activities (introducing points, badges, and leaderboards) and game-based learning activities (where students learn while playing) increase students' motivation to complete learning activities. However, how does this extra motivation help us as teachers to achieve the learning outcomes scheduled in the course? Are there any gamified activities that are best suited to achieve some results or others depending on the level of the goal set?

An interdisciplinary teaching innovation group at the UPC set out to work on game-based activities to achieve deeper learning by taking advantage of the extra doses of motivation that students show when participating in gamified activities.

2 The subject

Wave optics is a core subject and is taught in the second semester of the degree in optics and optometry at the School of optics and optometry in the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya. The first two semesters of the degree form the selective phase and therefore, the subject is part of this phase. The selective phase is a set of subjects that are assessed together and must be passed in a maximum period of twice their duration. In case of not passing the selective phase, the student cannot continue the degree.

⁵ <https://trainingindustry.com/articles/learning-technologies/game-based-learning-vs-gamification-do-you-know-the-difference/>

⁶ <https://www.forbes.com/advisor/banking/how-gamification-can-help-you-meet-financial-goals/>

The subject has 6 ECTS, which are transformed into 2 hours a week with the big group and 2 hours of laboratory work for approximately 15 weeks. The second semester of the degree is characterized by its hardness, many subjects with new content and many laboratory practice sessions. This fact, together with the fact that the contents are related to the fundamental aspects of the discipline and that it is difficult for students to see their application, leads us to the initial motivation for the subject being low.

In the normal period (2nd Q) 90 new students are enrolled. They are divided into two big groups (50 + 40) and seven groups of laboratories (x15). Attendance is very dissimilar among big groups and very high among all laboratory groups.

2.1 Contents

The subject has a syllabus that extends over the generation, propagation and detection of light. Themes are covered by considering light as an electromagnetic wave. The properties of the waves and how they are presented in the light are studied.

2.2 Methodology

Students have all the material they need to follow the course on the intranet. This material includes a detailed study guide with the activities to be carried out to learn the contents of the subject. The homework consists that the students have to write summaries of the contents to be treated in the subject from the reading of the chosen material, try to solve small exercises, share the exercises with the classmates and give them feedback, use some simulations to check the phenomena explained in class and solve some problems where the usual topics of the topic appear.

In the course, we propose for the big group sessions to combine expository classes with informal cooperative learning activities. Some of these activities are games (group quizzes where students get small rewards such as winning a race, ...) that seek to keep students up to date.

Completion of activities is also listed on a leaderboard that motivates students to stay up to date.

2.3 The laboratory

In the laboratory sessions, students carry out guided experiments to check the most important laws explained in the large group sessions.

In the laboratory, each group (3 people) has a set-up to do the experiments of the session and must be able to deliver at the end of the session a dossier with the completed report of the work. The dossier should consist of: a summary of the theory related to the experiment they will carry out, the numerical results, graphs, etc., the answers to small questions given in advance by the teacher and as a most important element, the conclusions and final comments of what they worked on in the session.

The groups work cooperatively, they deliver a single consensual dossier for which all members are responsible, exchange roles within the group (prepare reports alternately), conduct examinations individually, and are rewarded if the individual performance of all group members is high... The handout of the experiments tries to foster interaction within the group (discussion of outcome graphs, individual measurements and comparison of results...). Each week, students receive feedback from the teacher on reports from the previous session (Gibbs, 2005).

Laboratory sessions allow us to work on transversal competencies over relatively long periods. So, we spent the first half of the semester working on the written expression. In these laboratory sessions, students should write comments on the results (in the form of a graph) obtained explaining the observed behaviours. In the second half, we work on the accuracy and precision of the measurements. Students develop techniques to try to improve the accuracy of the measurements they make and to know the precision with which they make these measurements.

The experience of the last courses is that the laboratory sessions are very positive and beneficial for the performance of the students. The groups in the laboratory work very well and their overall performance improves a lot.

2.4 Assessment

The assessment of the subject is divided equally between the big group sessions and the laboratory sessions, as the time spent by the students in each one is the same.

The School of Optics and Optometry only reserves a time slot for each subject at the end of the semester to take exams in the big groups. All other tests are carried out during the hours assigned to the subject. In these spaces, we propose to the students four controls with a weight each of 10% of the final mark. There are two that are small multiple-choice tests where they also have to justify the chosen option. We dedicate 30 minutes to this. And two where in addition to the test they have to solve an exercise and justify the solution, this takes one hour.

At the end of the course, in the slot reserved by the School for the final assessment, students can repeat any of the tests they have taken during the semester. On this occasion, all the controls have a multi-response test part and an exercise.

The activities carried out during the semester (summaries, solving exercises, simulations ...) are assessed by the teacher at the end of the course if 80% of them have been completed on time. This assessment adds up to 10% of the final grade.

The most experimental part of the course is assessed with two laboratory exams (weighing 20% each) and a laboratory report grade (10%). Laboratory exams are conducted during a lab session and students must individually repeat a part of one of the experiments performed, write a small report with the results and answer some questions. The grade of the laboratory reports (10%) is proposed by the teacher at the end of the semester based on the reports delivered and the work done by the student in the laboratory sessions.

Figure 1.- Diagram of the assessment

We have tried to design an evaluation system that manages to engage the students in a continuous work from the beginning of the subject and until the end, some of the elements taken into account are (Armengol, 2007):

- Give opportunities to students to pass the subject until the last day.
- Not to eject students from the course until the end.
- Do not permit a student to pass the subject until the end.
- Give them the appropriate workload.
- Keep students informed of their performance
- Engage them in the course (hear their opinions, take them into account,...)
- Explain why the course is active.

▪ ...

3 Gaming

So far we have done gamification experiences like quizzes in class with electronic platforms, leaderboards of the homework,... which have shown us that students have an extra dose of motivation to participate in these activities.

The challenge of the new innovation project is to work on game-based activities in order to achieve deeper learning.

Although the variety of experiences and theories on which the games are based are very diverse⁷, we have set out to better develop the possibilities of game-based learning by redesigning the simulation activities that students carry out from the principles of McGonigal (2011) so that they are games from which they cannot escape without learning. The activity we found most appropriate to achieve this goal was a sequential escape room (Veldkamp, 2020). The simulation activities have been included in an escape room where students play in groups and to advance in the game they have to solve an enigma using the knowledge developed in the subject. As McGonigal proposes, the escape room seeks to have an epic mission, a clear goal, immediate feedback and another opportunity to prove it, and a positive social dimension.

3.1 The escape room

The escape room is a challenge: Students get on the train to come to the School (located in Terrassa, a city near Barcelona) and just as the train starts moving they hear a message from the driver that today the train will not stop in our city!!! "Just today my teammates have the most important commitment of the whole degree!!!". Students must advance on the train wagons until they reach the locomotive where the driver is to inform him that he must stop the train so that his classmates can come to school to carry out the most important activity of the year (Epic Mission). To cross each wagon (clear goal) the reviser asks them some questions that they must solve. In each car, the questions are on one of the topics of the subject and they can run some simulations to solve the problem. The questions you ask them are small exercises with multiple-choice options. At the end of all the questions in the wagon, they receive feedback on the result (immediate feedback) and if they have not answered all the questions correctly, they can try again (another chance to prove it). The game is played as a team (social dimension) and cooperation between team members is encouraged. They have one hour to complete the game, which is the train journey time.

3.2 The evaluation of the experience.

To evaluate the experience, we have added some questions to the traditional assessment surveys of each subject. Thus, having all the members of the team who participate in different subjects with different studies run the same questions, we can easily make comparisons.

The questions we propose to ask are:

Statement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
The game has been a motivation to start working on the subject	1	2	3	4	5
The game has engaged me to practice more	1	2	3	4	5
I have enjoyed learning through play	1	2	3	4	5
The game has helped me to acquire a deeper level of understanding	1	2	3	4	5
I like the fact that I could solve the problems at my own pace	1	2	3	4	5
Mention three positive aspects that you have enjoyed					
Mention three shortcomings or things that you would improve					

⁷ Valero, Miguel. <https://personals.ac.upc.edu/miguel/materiales/docencia/articulos/Gamificacion.pdf>

4 Preliminary results

Preliminary results of the survey are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2.- Results of the survey. The vertical axis indicates the number of groups (each group having 3-4 students).

Access to the survey presented in the previous chapter was given once finished the escape room. Groups, the same ones who had participated in the game, answered it. There is only one answer per group. Each group consisted of between 3 and 4 students.

The processed results and discussion of the individual and joint surveys will be presented at the conference.

Acknowledgement

This work has been supported by the Institut de Ciències de l'Educació (ICE) Convocatòria de projectes d'innovació docent 2021 (Acord CG/2021/02/34, de 9 d'abril de 2021) and by the Escola Tècnica Superior d'Enginyeria de Telecomunicació de Barcelona (upc telecoms-UPC-Tech).

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